

Table S2. The sequences of the CEL-Seq primers. The 8 base barcodes are as previously published, the 6 base barcodes are listed in the detailed protocol.

CEL-Seq	CGATTGAGGCCGGTAATACGACTCACTATAGGGGTTCA GAGTTCTACAGTCCGACGATC[8 base barcode]TTTTTTTTTTTTTTTTTTTTTTTTT
CEL-Seq + UMI	CGATTGAGGCCGGTAATACGACTCACTATAGGGGTTCA GAGTTCTACAGTCCGACGATCNNNNN[6 base barcode]TTTTTTTTTTTTTTTTTTTTTTTTT
CEL-Seq2	GCCGGTAATACGACTCACTATAGGGAGTTCTACAGTCC GACGATCNNNNNN[6 base barcode]TTTTTTTTTTTTTTTTTTTTTTTTT
Library RT primer	GCCTTGGCACCCGAGAATTCCANNNNNN